

Deliverable D6.1

Project handbook (v1.1)

Document Summary Information

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Executive summary:

This *Project Handbook* establishes the governance framework and operational guidelines for the Consortium. Its primary objective is to equip partners¹ with a comprehensive roadmap of the project's management structure, non-technical procedures, and individual responsibilities to ensure high-quality outcomes. Key sections include internal communication protocols, decision-making and conflict resolution workflows, financial and technical reporting standards, and mandatory dissemination obligations. Additionally, it provides essential guidelines on quality assurance (Q&A) for deliverables and gender neutrality.

¹ While the current deliverable is addressed to the project' partners, an internal Welcome Pack will be issued by Month 07. This document will provide essential information and guidance for the recruited Doctoral Candidates.

Revision history

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² To ensure high standards of communication and linguistic consistency, the drafting process included stylistic refinement assisted by Gemini (Google AI)

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³ Credits: Figures 3 and 4 are sourced from Horizon Europe Guidelines “MSCA Doctoral Networks 2024, Factsheets for coordinators & project Managers”

List of Acronyms

APM	Administrative Project Manager; the person designated by i2CAT to assist in the coordination of the financial, legal, organizational and administrative tasks of the project
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCC	Country Correction Coefficients to adjust the researcher's living allowance based on the cost of living in the host country relative to Belgium. These coefficients, listed in the Horizon Europe Work Programme, are applied directly to the base living allowance for all MSCA actions
DC	Doctoral Candidate
DoA	Description of the Action (Annex I to the contract)
EC	European Commission
EEA	External Ethics Advisor
EU	European Union
F&T	European Commission Funding and Tenders Portal, usually known as EU Participant Portal
GA	Grant Agreement
MD	Mobility Declaration
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Person month
PO	Project Officer (EC's supervisor of the Action)
REA	(European) Research Executive Agency
SB	Supervisory Board
TL	Task Leader
UC	Unit Costs
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

GENOME is a Horizon Europe (HE) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Networks (MSCA-DN) Action coordinated by i2CAT that comprehends a consortium of twelve EU beneficiaries (10) and associated partners (2):

FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA (i2CAT),
NEC LABORATORIES EUROPE GMBH (NEC),
OULUN YLIOPISTO (OULU),
INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN (IJS),
TELEFONICA INNOVACION DIGITAL SL (TID),
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA (UPC),
POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS (TUC),
FOGUS INNOVATIONS & SERVICES P.C. (FOG),
L.M. ERICSSON LIMITED (LMI),
ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTRIAKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON (UOA),
MEDNARODNA PODIPLOMSKA SOLA JOZEFA STEFANA (MPS) and
TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY OF THE SHANNON: MIDLANDS MIDWEST (TUS)

Project full title:	GENerative and connected intelligence for 6G Open ManagemEnt
Project acronym:	GENOME
Contract number:	HE Grant Agreement nº 101226860
Call and Topic:	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-DN-01-01
Type of Action:	HORIZON TMA MSCA Doctoral Networks
Granting authority:	European Research Executive Agency
Start date:	01/01/2026
End date:	31/12/2029
Eligible contribution:	4.258.518,48 €
Max. grant amount:	4.258.518,48 €
Form of the grant:	Unit Costs

1.1 Purpose, scope and structure

This deliverable D6.1 contains the Management Guidelines designed to provide the Consortium with essential information regarding work organization, applicable regulations and procedures.

The objective of this handbook is to outline the project's management structure, tasks, and responsibilities, as well as guidelines for non-technical implementation to support the implementation of this ambitious Doctoral Network.

Key topics include:

- Project structure and reference documents
- Collaborative tools and internal communication
- Meetings, decision-making, and conflict resolution
- Project and financial reporting procedures
- Deliverable quality assurance
- Dissemination obligations and output reporting
- Doctoral Candidates' recruitment guidelines
- Gender-neutral issues and recommendations

D6.1 is a living document and will be updated internally when needed.

1.2 Precedence and Reference documents

The established procedures, are based on the general principles and policies defined in underlying basic regulations:

- Horizon Europe Framework Programme Guide [Ref. 1],
- specific Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2025 for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions [Ref. 3],
- The HE Financial Guide on MSCA Actions [Ref. 2]
- contracts and agreements [Ref. 4], [Ref. 5] [Ref. 6],

and are aimed to assure quality implementation of GENOME. Where necessary or convenient, specific references are given.

The general principles for the project execution have been defined in the Grant Agreement (EC-GA), the Description of the Action (DoA) and in the Consortium Agreement (CA) provisions.

The Project Management handbook shall not replace any of the established agreements within the consortium or with the EC, or any of the EC guidelines for project implementation and documentation. Where there are any apparent or real inconsistencies between these documents the following order of precedence will be applied:

1. Grant Agreement with European Commission (EC) and its annexes [Ref. 4][Ref. 5]
2. Consortium Agreement [Ref. 6]
3. Project handbook D6.1

If doubts persist, they have to be resolved by decisions of the Supervisory Board.

1.2.1 Grant Agreement

The **Grant Agreement (EC-GA)** defines the contractual obligations set by European Commission (EC). It defines the rights and obligations together with the terms and conditions that are applicable to the grant awarded and the beneficiaries and associated partners who will be implementing the action. It is signed by the EC and the beneficiaries of the action.

It has nine parts:

- Preamble
- Terms and Conditions
- Project Data Sheet
- Dispositions from Chapter 1 to Chapter 6

- Annex 1 Description of the action (DoA)
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action
- Annex 3 Accession Forms
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements⁴
- Annex 5 Specific rules

Modifications of the Grant Agreement dispositions must be approved by the Supervisory Board and by the EC. It must be requested as an amendment to the document. If approved, the latest version of the document will be uploaded to the Participant Portal and to the internal document repository of the project (Repository folder in Sharepoint [Ref. 8], see Section 4.1).

Figure 1: What the GA is? (extracted from the EU-PO presentation at the GENOME's KoM)

1.2.2 Contract amendments

Contract amendments are coordinated by the Administrative Project Manager of the consortium (appointed by i2CAT). Any change affecting the contract leads to a major review of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes and requires a high level of interaction with the EC Project Officer (EC-PO) and the project partners.

Events that require or trigger contract amendments are:

- Beneficiaries / associated partners **joining or leaving the consortium** (it includes changes at legal and financial level of the current beneficiaries) or changes due to partial takeover, etc
- Adjusting project duration or reporting periods
- Relevant changes in the detailed work plan.
- Other

The amendment request consists of:

- updated structured information on the Grant Management System screens
- amendment request letter: the letter with the request and reasons for the amendment
- amendment core (including new version of EC-GA Annexes 1 and 2, if needed): the legal document with the list of amendment clauses

⁴ See Annex 2a on Additional information on unit costs and contributions

- supporting documents: documents uploaded by the consortium, consolidated Grant Agreement, etc

Relocation or resignation of key personnel does not lead to an amendment of the contract if it does not require the change of budgets, objectives, the work plan or the inclusion / exclusion of a beneficiary. The APM has to notify such changes to the EC-PO.

1.3 Financial, legal and administrative data confidential treatment

The Project Coordination understands and values the privacy of all project partners. Any sensitive information shared during queries—specifically regarding salaries, personal data, or internal institutional matters—with the APM and/or the Project Coordination will be treated with strict confidentiality. Any shared documentation will be stored in accordance with privacy regulations, utilizing secure electronic folders accessible only to the GENOME APM.

1.3.1 Consortium Agreement

The CA is an **internal agreement between the consortium members, including Beneficiaries and Associated Partners**. Its purpose is to specify the organization of the consortium, the distribution of work, project management, and the financial agreements reached for redistributing the Management unit costs. Additionally, it covers rights and obligations related to background and results, the settlement of internal disputes, and arrangements for liability, indemnification, and confidentiality.

Any further changes to the CA must be agreed upon by all partners.

1.3.2 Additional documentation

To facilitate project management, additional information regarding financial and administrative management, dissemination guidelines, and other relevant documents will be regularly uploaded to the management section (WP6 folder) of the project repository [Ref. 8].

2. Project structure and reference documents

2.1 Management structure's overview

This section describes the management structure and the different bodies and roles that ensure a proper implementation of the action. The underlying objective is to facilitate the day-to-day activity, define the responsibilities that allow a monitoring of the action in order to prevent conflicts.

To simplify partners' load of work but at the same time keep track of on-going progress, the project structure was kept intentionally simple, avoiding standing committees, thematic sub-teams or working groups.

Following this line, the main responsibilities stand on the **Supervisory Board (SB, composed by a representative of each partner) the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium**, responsible for strategic project management issues. This governing body counts on two main additional bodies: on one hand the **Recruitment Committee (RC)** overseeing a transparent and gender-balanced recruitment process and the WP Leaders (WPL) are responsible of coordinating activities within the work packages.

Due to the sensitivity and high interdependency of the work carried out in the different WPs, the Project Management (WP) plays an important role as coordinator and facilitator of communication, moderator of debates and controller of Objectives and Work Plan. The **Coordinator (PC)** of GENOME is backed by an experienced **Administrative Project Manager (APM)** that support in the overall consortium management.

Figure 2: GENOME management structure

Normal roles and governing bodies of the project are presented in the above figure.

Table 1: GENOME Governing Bodies

Supervisory Board (SB)	Responsible of the final decisions on the overall policies of the consortium
Chaired by	The Project Coordinator (PC)
Participants	One representative of each Partner + two Doctoral Candidate Representatives ⁵
Meeting frequency	At least once a year, ideally twice a year
Main tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Management and monitoring of the project progress. Is responsible for setting the overall project strategy ⇒ Monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project, evaluate the progress against the planned milestones ⇒ Oversee the quality and quantity of supervision of the DCs, approve the Career Development Plan agreed by the supervisors and the DC and approve the DC s’ recruitment procedure of the Recruitment Committee ⇒ Support the PC and the APM in preparing the meetings with the funding authorities and in preparing deliverables. ⇒ Oversee the gender issues, monitor ethics and GDPR issues ⇒ Track the achievements of technical milestones, monitor technical risks. ⇒ Content, Finances and intellectual property rights: changes to the annexes 1 and 2 of the GA, changes of the consortium plan.

⁵ DC representatives are invited to attend and participate in deliberations (no voting rights) when the agenda of a SB meeting includes items concerning training activities, secondments and / or career plans.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Evolution of the consortium: Entry of a new Party, withdrawal of party, identification of a breach by a Party. ⇒ Breach, defaulting party status and litigation
Recruitment Committee (RC)	Responsible for the overseeing of recruiting process, ensuring strict adherence to the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers
Chaired by	The Project Coordinator (PC)
Participants	DC’s Supervisors + four external experts, two from academia and two from the industry.
Meeting frequency	As needed, at least monthly during the first phase of the hiring process
Main tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Oversee that the recruitment is an open and transparent process based solely on merit ⇒ Keep records on the recruitment process to prove compliance with EU -GA requirements, namely in the positions descriptions an the advertising in international channels ⇒ Collaborate and assess with each recruiting institution to make the final decision of recruited DC’s ⇒ Oversee the gender and GDPR issues during the recruitment process

Table 2: GENOME Managerial individual roles

Project Coordinator (PC, i2CAT)	Intermediary between the EC and the consortium, it will control and coordinate the project and the project reporting
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Monitor compliance by the partners with their obligations. ⇒ Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Funding ⇒ Transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned ⇒ Coordinate the communication and ease the flow of information among partners and all requested reports within the deadlines agreed upon with the EC ⇒ Jointly with the APM. act as the intermediary for all communications between the beneficiaries and the Commission ⇒ Prepare the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the SB ⇒ Jointly with the WP Leaders, coordination of the technical work and the technical issues of EC reviews ⇒ Coordinate jointly with the WP Leaders the content and timing of joint publications
Admin, Legal and Financial (APM, i2CAT)	Support the PC and the GA in the administrative, legal, organizational and financial duties
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Assist the Project Coordinator in the project management tasks.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Manage the delivery and the follow-up of administrative and financial documents ⇒ Administer the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7 of the CA ⇒ Permanent contact point for the Coordinator and all the Partners regarding the formalities of the participation in the project and requests and maintaining a high level of communication within the Consortium. ⇒ Provides support and assistance to all partners. ⇒ Submit the deliverables and reports to the Commission
Work Package Leaders (WPLs⁶)	Responsible for planning and supervising the progress of work within their Work Package, coordinating the inputs of the involved partners
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Oversees the implementation of the DCs careers involved in the WP ⇒ Supervising quality and timeliness of deliverables ⇒ Coordinating the KPI surveillance and production of reports at WP level ⇒ Observing compliance with the ethics provisions as well as events or results affecting IPR issues ⇒ Detecting deviations, prepare measures and report them to the SB
Task Leaders	Responsible for concrete tasks, planning and monitoring the progress of work within its task, as well as the contributions of the involved partners
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Organising and steering the task development ⇒ Keeping direct supervision of the DCs involved ⇒ Contributing to the reporting duties at task level ⇒ Supporting the WPL in the coordination of the different teams inside the WP ⇒ Participating in the coordination of the WP meetings

2.1.1 Additional boards

Additional boards for the implementation of the project may be created and called by SB to clarify topics of their competence that require some external view.

2.2 Conflicts

Maintaining goodwill and acting in good faith are foundational to the success of the GENOME project. To prevent major disruptions caused by conflicts of interest, we prioritise the coordination of actions across all levels, supervisors and work packages. This proactive approach ensures that consensus is achieved during the early stages of development.

In instances where partners identify conflicts that cannot be resolved through bilateral communication, the matter must be immediately escalated to the Project Coordinator (PC). If the dispute pertains to technical implementation, the relevant Work Package (WP) Leader should also be notified. Ultimately, any critical or deadlock decisions will be adjudicated by the project’s highest authority: the Supervisory Board.

⁶ i2CAT (WP6), NEC (WP1), IJS (WP2), OULU (WP3), TID (WP4) and UPC (WP5)

2.3 Events that must be immediately reported

Partners must immediately inform the Project Coordinator (PC) of any issues likely to significantly impact the project's implementation or the EU's financial interests. When needed, the PC will inform the EU Project Officer (EU-PO) and the wider Consortium. Reportable events include:

- Changes in the secondments plans, the Principal Investigator (PI) or Supervisor (SUP)
- Institutional Shifts: Changes in the legal, financial, technical, organizational, or ownership status of a beneficiary or its linked third parties
- Administrative Updates: Any change to the name, address, legal form, or organization type of linked third parties
- Eligibility & Compliance: Any circumstance affecting the original decision to award the grant or the ongoing compliance with the Grant Agreement.
- Acquired ineligibility or changes in the family status of a DC

Each partner will maintain accurate, up-to-date information in the Participant Portal, specifically regarding legal representatives and organizational status.

3. Reporting

Reporting is the way to track GENOME project progress and a condition for payment. This section explains the continuous and periodic reporting obligations, how to fill-in the Mobility Declaration, and how it ties into financial statements and reimbursements.

Reporting is a continuous activity and a fundamental contractual obligation that requires every partner to provide requested information in a timely manner.

The administrative execution period is fractioned into 2 reporting periods (RP) according to EC standards:

RP1: from M01 to M24 (January 2026 – December 2027)

RP2: from M25 to PM48 (January 2028 – December 2029), tied to the payment's timeline:

Figure 3:
Reporting and
Payments timeline
presentation at
the GENOME's
KoM)

Within the execution period (48 months) the reporting, deliverables and planning cycles consist of:

- **Continuous reporting:** Opens at the start of the project to provide regular updates on the status of the Action.
- **Mobility tab, individual financial statements & Reports**
- **Mid-term "check":** meeting between the REA service and the GENOME consortium (M13-M15)
- **Periodic reporting:** to the EC have to be generated for every reporting period and are due 60 days after the end of the corresponding reporting period. The reports contain cost claims (based on Unit Costs declarations).

- **Project reviews** are meetings between part of the consortium led by the Coordinator and the EC (usually assisted by External experts) and form part of the periodic EC project review procedure to be finished normally at the latest 60 days after the reporting period. In the case of the final review the meeting may take place before the final reports are finished, i.e. at the latest 60 days after the end of the project⁷, in order to provide input and support to the generation of the final reports.

Figure 4: Reporting duties diagram

To maintain unified standard across the consortium, **English remains the mandated language** for all project-related deliverables, reports, and internal written communications. The only permitted exceptions to this rule are dissemination materials, such as press releases or technical publications, which partners may translate into other languages at their own discretion and responsibility.

For documents such deliverables (guidelines are presented in section 5) each individual partner remains strictly accountable for the quality and accuracy of their specific contributions. **The editor of a document holds the broader responsibility for the overall quality of the work**, which includes managing communication procedures, coordinating the collection of input from various parties, and integrating those pieces into final releases.

Ultimately, the Coordinator serves as the official liaison to the European Commission, holding the sole responsibility for the formal submission of all official project documentation.

3.1 Continuous reporting

Purpose:

Continuous reporting on the progress of the action (opens at the start of the project and allows the submission of deliverables, publications, etc. – see the diagram in Figure 4)

Format and duties:

⁷ This period may be extended to 90 days after the end of the project upon request.

3.2 Mobility tab, individual financial statements & Reports

Purpose:

The **Mobility Declaration** records the periods that a person, for work or study reasons, spends at an institution or company in the context of a Grant Agreement. This tab is used to:

- collect the **Mobility Declarations**: the beneficiaries are required to promptly inform the EU about the persons taking part in the grants, their periods spent at an institution and their mode of involvement with the grant
- collect information to allow a semi-automated calculation of the funding that beneficiaries will receive as a reimbursement of the costs incurred in the context of people mobility.

The **Mobility** tab is part of the [Continuous Report](#), and the collected data are then included in the [Periodic Report](#) and used for the preparation of Financial Statements.

Researchers

Researcher ID	First Name	Family Name	Gender	Birthdate	Nationality	Submitted Declarations	Actions
1	Konstantinos	RIZOS	M	15/03/2023	BE - Belgium	0 out of 1	
2	Another	Name	NB	14/03/2023	AG - Antigua and Barbuda	0 out of 0	

Mobility Declarations

Number	Researcher ID	First Name	Family Name	Destination Organisation	Start date	End date	Contract Type	Family charges	Working Time Commitment	Duration	Status	Actions
1	1	Konstantinos	RIZOS	AST ADVANCED SPACE TEC	15/03/2023	14/09/2025	A. Employment contract	Yes	Suspension for maternity Full Time	17.500000	DRAFT	

Secondments

Researcher ID	First Name	Family Name	Sending Organisation	Sector of Send. Org.	Sending Country	Secondment Organisation	Sector of Sec. Org.	Secondment Country	Start date	End date	Working Time Commitment	Working time percentage	Duration	Actions
1	1	Konstantinos	RIZOS	AST ADVANCED SPACE	Academic	Germany	CENTRE NATIONAL DE	Academic	France	16/09/2021	10/12/2021		0	

How to:

The mobility tab has **3 sections** where you need to provide information about the recruited researchers.

1. **“Researchers”** where the researcher’s personal details are added. - Researcher’s data can be imported from the My Person Profile in the Funding &Tenders Portal (if available).

- If not, information will need to be encoded manually.
- Researcher should be requested to register to My Person Profile.
- It is also under the Researcher tab that information is encoded if the recruited researcher is entitled to a Special Needs Allowance (SNLS).

2. **“Mobility Declaration” (MD)** contains the researcher’s information which is linked to the **recruiting institution** and specifies the **recruitment period(s)**. - It allows for the **automatic calculation of worked person-months (PMs)**, which are the basis for the **Individual Financial Statement** (submitted by each beneficiary at the end of each reporting period and automatically generated based on the MD).

The MD must be submitted within 20 days after the recruitment of each researcher and updated (if needed) before the submission of the periodic reports.

- If ‘submitted’, only the recruitment period can be edited, and secondments added.

- In case of change of the family status, contract type, and addition of a special needs allowance, a **new Mobility Declaration** will need to be submitted (if it doesn't apply to the whole recruitment).
- In case of change on the work-time commitment, the same Mobility Declaration will need to be used but a **new recruitment period** added.
- An assessment of the budget needs will be carried out by the granting authority; in case of need, an **increase of the budget** will be implemented through an amendment (e.g., addition of family, long-term or leave or special needs allowance).

3. **“Secondments”** where secondments are encoded (once they have taken place).

Please refer to the [EU F&T IT How to](#) for detailed information on the required inputs. In case of doubt the APM remains at the disposal of all the beneficiaries for questions and support before to escalating any issue to the REA services desk.

Beneficiaries are strongly encouraged to share their drafts with the APM for review and validation before final submission. This proactive step helps ensure data consistency and avoids the need for corrections once the information is locked in the Portal

3.3 Mid-term “check”

Purpose:

The main objective of the Mid-term Check is to evaluate the recruitment process and verify fellow eligibility. Additionally, it serves to raise awareness regarding the rights and obligations of both beneficiaries and fellows, assess any project deviations, and establish necessary contingency plans where applicable.

This milestone requires that all fellows have been successfully recruited and that the formal Progress Report has been submitted.

How to:

The PC is responsible for organizing a *Mid-Term* meeting **between Months 13 and 15**, in accordance with the Work Programme and Article 25 of the Grant Agreement.

The meeting is contingent upon the successful recruitment of all fellows and the formal submission of the Progress Report. Its primary objectives are to evaluate recruitment and fellow eligibility, while ensuring all beneficiaries and fellows are fully aware of their respective rights and obligations. Furthermore, the session serves to assess any project deviations and define necessary contingency plans where applicable.

3.4 Periodic Reporting

Purpose:

At the end of each reporting period, and in order to receive payments, the consortium must submit periodic reports (following the schedule set out in the Grant Agreement: after M24 and M48).

When these are due, they must be submitted directly in the Periodic Reporting Module of the Portal Grant Management System.

The APM will send guidelines and templates.

Composition:

The Periodic report consists on:

- **Technical report** which has 2 parts:
 - Part A: automatically generated based on data encoded in the Continuous and Periodic Reporting.
 - Part B: narrative description of work's progress (the template will be available in the reporting module when the reporting module is launched).
- **Financial statements** – individual: they are automatically generated based on the PMs declared in the Mobility Declaration (costs are not editable).

3.5 Project reviews

Purpose and Timing:

The REPA (reporting and payment workflow) **opens at the end of each reporting period:**

- **Objective:** assess the project's progress via an interim / final review based on the technical report submitted and the Individual Financial Statements (IFS), automatically generated based on the information encoded in the Mobility Declaration;

Reviews are done remotely unless otherwise agreed with REA;

They can be carried out with the help of an external expert.

The assessment of the work is done based on the periodic report submitted which is a precondition to receive payments.

Assessment outcome:

- **Report acceptance OR**
- **Report rejection:** request for revisions or additional information, which triggers a suspension of the payment deadline. Once revisions are accepted by REA, the payment is released.

4. Project collaborative tools, internal communication and meetings

4.1 Project repository

As an internal collaborative platform to store and share all the documentation produced by the project (deliverables, agendas, action points, presentations) a **secured SharePoint space** [Ref. 8] hosted by i2CAT was chosen.

The Project Coordinator (PC) and Work Package Leaders (WPLs) hold the ultimate responsibility for ensuring the quality, coherence, and structural order of all project-related content. Beyond acting as a document repository, the collaborative workspace serves as a central hub for team organization and the ongoing coordination of work packages. Access to this platform is systematically managed by the Administrative Project Manager (APM), who is responsible for granting permissions and maintaining the integrity of the shared environment for all consortium partners.

The repository has the following folders:

- 00 Proposal - ESR: the final version of the submitted proposal as well as the result of the evaluation by the EU services
- 01 Contractual documents: Grant Agreement (amendment when applicable) and Consortium Agreement
- 02 Templates: it contains templates for the deliverables, presentations, call of the meetings and minutes
- 03 Budget and Payments
- 04 Meetings:
 - F2F meetings and on-line meetings (regular or not): *minutes, agendas, presentations* and *logistic indications* (accommodation, maps and indications), scanned signature sheets regarding the meetings.
 - Actions Points excel: it lists all the open and closed action points.
 - Calendars: National holidays EU countries, Plenary meetings calendar for the full project duration
- 05 Reporting folder: this section will be used to gather the information of the periodic Interim reports. It will include the definitive version of the Periodic and Final Reports.
- 06 Deliverables: contents the definitive versions of each of the deliverables submitted (in both, editable and final PDF formats). Collaborative work to prepare the releases is done in the respective subfolder of each WP.
- Work Packages 1-5 folders: each folder includes the working versions of the deliverables and other working documents, as well as up to date information on the on-going work in every WP. A subfolder details every Deliverable detail (e.g., due date, name)
- WP6 – Management folder, among other sub-files, the folder contains useful information on guidelines, EU communications and other management files.
- WP7 – Impact and Dissemination folder, among other sub-files, the folder contains posters and the official logos of the project and the partners for:
 - Dissemination Material: leaflets, presentations, video clips and other outreach material. The section will also include the press releases generated by the project
 - Papers and presentations: to store all scientific outputs
 - *Conference Calls*: Summary of each conference call including attendees, discussion items and actions points.

4.2 Directory and mailing lists

A comprehensive **Project Directory**, containing the primary contact details and specific roles of all participants, is maintained within the **GENOME Repository** root folder via the **Project Masterfile** [Ref. 10]. While this document remains accessible for updates at any time, it is imperative that the **APM** be formally notified of any modifications. This ensures that all synchronized administrative tools, including distribution lists, automated mailing groups, and collated internal sheets—remain accurate and up to date across the entire consortium.

The email communication reflector of the project is hosted by i2CAT (as Coordinator), who maintains the following email lists:

Table 3: GENOME Mailing Lists

List name	Members	Email address
GENOME (all)	General Project’s R&D and admin staff	[REDACTED]
GENOME (SB)	Supervisory Board members and proxy staff	[REDACTED]
GENOME (RC)	Mailing list for the Recruitment Committee	[REDACTED]
GENOME (DC)	Mailing list with all the recruited Doctoral Candidates	[REDACTED]
GENOME (admin)	Admin, legal, contractual and financial issues	[REDACTED]

All emails sent to the different mailing lists automatically include a prefix text in brackets in the subject (e.g. [GENOME_all], [GENOME_RC], etc.) for better scope/topic identification. The purpose of this set of emails is to offer the possibility to reach smaller groups, a more focused way to exchange information between the different boards, groups or WPs that compose the project.

In case a new member joins the project, the user should either include the person in the Directory file [Ref. 10] or send an email with the specific request to the APM who will activate the accession to the repository and internal communication chat.

4.3 Slack channel

Slack is the main tool for direct / fast non-formal communication between partners. Everyone will have the option to start private conversations and channels in the tool in order to accelerate the discussions and make the collaboration progress more effective.

Moreover, everyone will be able to post messages to the “General” channel and the channels created for each specific work package if needed to avoid spam.

4.4 Conference Calls

Dedicated conference bridges (Zoom / Teams licence hosted by i2CAT) are provided by i2CAT to facilitate remote connections at the plenary virtual meetings and the Project Reviews.

Additional ad-hoc conference calls should be regulated by the following general rules:

- The partners will schedule the date of the conference, using also appropriate support tools. (e.g., doodle).
- An invitation to the project email list with the exact time, agenda and information on how to join the conference call will be circulated, at least one day before the conference call.
- When scheduling a recurring meeting using an emailing list, the meeting caller shall regularly check that the eventual new members of the list area added manually.

4.5 Supervisory Board gatherings

Regular SB meetings will take place ideally twice a year⁹ chaired by the PC. The partner’s SB representative/s and proxy should in principle be maintained throughout the project, where this is possible. Any change in a partner’s representative to the SB should be informed by email to the APM at

⁹ Extraordinary meetings or phone conferences may be called by the PC, when necessary

least 10 days before a meeting of the SB takes place, indicating the reason for substitution, identifying the new representative and explaining whether the substitution will be temporary or permanent.

Partners will propose the hosting the 2F2 meetings on a voluntary basis to spread organisational costs.

Plenary meetings' dates and venues for the full project duration to be scheduled by month 04 latest.

The exact dates are fixed at least 3 months ahead of time in order to avoid travel calendar conflicts¹⁰. The agenda is generated by the PC in agreement with the WPL inputs. It is distributed to the partners and when applicable the DC representatives at least 3 weeks prior to the assembly (ten natural days in case of extraordinary meeting). Every beneficiary organizes and pays for his own travel. Expenses can be charged against the project.

The meetings may consist of 2 parts: a series of “all hands” sessions to present and discuss technical developments and a formal part where strategic and administrative decisions are taken.

As an outcome of SB assemblies, the PC, with the support of the WPLs generates minutes that reflect all relevant points of discussion, actions and decisions taken. A draft of these minutes shall be available to the members of the SB not later than 10 calendar days after the assembly and comments and feedback shall be given to the PC - APM not later than one week after that. After this date, non-response is taken to be agreement.

The final version of the minutes is fixed on the Project Repository not later than 2-3 weeks after the assembly.

4.5.1 *Hosting a face-to-face meeting*

When any beneficiary hosts a project meeting, the following points must be taken into consideration:

- It is advisable that the location can be easily reachable to avoid extra costs. The hosting partner shall provide logistic information on how to reach the venue of the meeting. The hosting partner shall also prepare meeting rooms equipped with audio-visual devices necessary for the presentations and network connectivity.
- The costs for hosting the meeting will be covered by the hosting partner and the travel costs will be covered by each participant.

It is also recommended (general practice although not obligatory) to provide water, as well as to organize lunch buffets if appropriate to the duration of the meeting.

4.6 **Eventual cross-dissemination and concertation meetings**

The SB Members will pay strong attention to eventual cross-dissemination and concertation meetings to foster communication with related projects within the same specific MSCA - DN work programme and call, organised by the EC. Any related and eligible cost occurred needs to be charged on the budget of each concerned partner.

5. Deliverables

This section describes the procedure to complete the deliverables that ought to be submitted during the project. Deliverables must be submitted in due time (end of the month indicated in the DoA). Although in

¹⁰ As indicated in the Consortium Agreement, the chairperson shall give notice in writing of a meeting to each member as soon as possible and no later than 14 calendar days preceding the meeting, or 7 calendar days before an extraordinary meeting.

GENOME deliverables are either labelled as *Report (R)*, as *Data Management Plan (DMP)* or *Other*, a written document must be submitted.

The Dissemination level is *PU* (public) or *SEN* (restricted to the EC and members of the Consortium). In the case of *public* deliverables, once submitted to the EC, the definitive content will be published in the CORDIS portal. If there are no substantiated objections, public deliverables will be uploaded to the project webpage and the Zenodo community of the project [Ref. 9].

5.1 Deliverable Quality Assurance

The Deliverable template [Ref. 11] is provided in the project Repository

A quality assurance process will be implemented for assuring a correct final output. For doing so, the consortium has allocated the following responsibilities within the consortium:

- **Main editor:** will be responsible for providing both the ToC and the main content for the deliverable and monitor the contributions from the rest of the contributors. They will also be in charge of making the necessary changes suggested by the reviewers.
- **Contributors:** will participate in the deliverable and will amend their content, if necessary, based on the guidelines from the main editor and the reviewers.
- **Reviewers:** up to two partners that will do the first review.

And the final assignment table of Deliverables is to be ready by Month 04 latest (April 2026). To date, all the deliverables for year 1 have already been assigned [Ref. 10].

The internal workflow for deliverables is the following one:

Table 4: Deliverables generation work-flow

Action	Days to deadline	Responsible	Receiver
TOC, section assignment to contributors	60	Lead (editor)	Contributors + WPL involved + PC
First draft of the deliverable + initial feedback from editor	45	Lead (editor)	Partners involved + WPL involved
Second consolidated draft of the deliverable	30	Lead (editor)	Partners involved + WPL involved + PC
Final draft (ready to be send to reviewers)	20	Lead (editor)	Partners involved + WPL involved + PC
Reviewers feedback	15	Reviewers.	Editor
Revised inputs	10	All authors	Editor
Final consolidated draft	4	Editor	APM ¹¹
Submission in the EU Portal	0-4	PC - APM	EU

5.2 Editorial and Quality criteria

The **editor / contributor** must consider the following criterions:

- **Completeness.** The deliverable must address all aspects related to the purpose and scope for which the related research activity is carried out.

¹¹ Formatting is to be re-checked by the APM before the submission of the document

- **Depth.** Each deliverable should have a coherent depth of information with respect to the deliverable scope, purpose and type of research activity described in the DoA.
- **Accuracy.** The information provided in the deliverables should be supported accurate and reliable information. All background information should be linked to appropriate references. *Results* information should be clearly described and technically supported.
- **Coherence.** Each deliverable must be produced using a common project template to have a uniform appearance and structure.

In addition, the **reviewer** will have to make sure that every deliverable is of the greatest quality, paying close attention to the deliverable's, structure, and content specifically, and has to verify the following formal checkpoints:

- ✓ That the deliverable includes an executive summary and proper conclusions if necessary.
- ✓ The contribution of each partner involved is correctly reported.
- ✓ The impact of the deliverable and any progress beyond the state-of-the-art is clearly identified, and any expected output (paper, patents, standard...) is included.
- ✓ Clear language is used, appropriate abbreviations and references are included and listed, a logical order has to be followed and the document follows the style template¹⁷ [Ref. 11].

5.2.1 Legibility guidelines

To ensure the maximum clarity and readability of each deliverable, consortium members are encouraged to follow the writing instructions below:

- **Cross-references:** Include cross-references in the document when linking to other sections of the text, figures, or tables.
- **Use of bullets:** It is highly recommended for structuring content or creating lists.
- **Use of Acronyms:** when referring to long names after the initial mention of it. The meaning of the acronym should be added in the initial List of Acronyms Section.
- **Avoid repeating content:** keep the document concise, simple, and easy to read by minimizing repetitive information.
- **Check format:** make sure that the header and footer, titles and subtitles and titles of figures and tables follow the same format throughout the document for those not specified in the template.

5.3 Sensitive deliverables

Sensitive refers to information that is considered private to the GENOME's Consortium. The partners shall maintain the confidentiality of any data, documents, or other materials that are designated as sensitive following the confidentiality guidelines included in the CA.

The following **disclaimer** needs to be present in the **cover page** of every deliverable that is confidential:

This document contains sensitive information, which is proprietary to the GENOME Consortium. Neither this document nor the information contained herein shall be used, copied, duplicated, reproduced, modified, or communicated by any means to any third party, in whole or in parts, except with prior written consent of the GENOME Consortium. In such case, an acknowledgement of the authors of the document and all applicable portions of the copyright notice must be clearly referenced. In the event of infringement, the consortium reserves the right to take any legal action it deems appropriate.

6. Project dissemination

Dissemination of the results, whenever is possible and suitable, is one of the projects objectives [Ref. 5]. Dissemination must not collide with the IPR of the partners or with results that ought to be protected.

In this section we describe the mandatory rules for disseminating the results of the project. Dissemination strategy will be further complemented by deliverables D7.1 and D7.2 (Plan for *Dissemination, communication and exploitation of results, including communication activities* interim and final in M13 and M48 respectively) and D6.3 (*Data Management Plan*, M13).

6.1 Acknowledgements

All the publications, conference proceedings, presentations on workshops, seminars, press releases, equipment, communications, patents, standard or public events must consider the below obligations towards the EC (see articles 17.2 and 17.3 of the EC-GA).

17.2

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

17.3

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

The obligation relates not only documents but also **infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results**. Suggested text:

“This project (work) has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101226860, GENOME and MSCA-DN Action. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them”.

6.2 Open Access mandate

All peer-reviewed scientific publications arising from Horizon Europe funding have to be made **available in open access**. This implies that outputs (publications and other) are to be:

- made **freely available online**, immediately upon publication and with no restrictions on use (licences like CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND or CC BY-NC ND or equivalent),
- managed in line with the **FAIR principles** of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability and
- deposited on a **trusted repository**, , even when publishing in an open access journal¹².

To facilitate effective management of research outputs within the GENOME project, a dedicated ‘**project community**’ has been established in **ZENODO**¹³. Curated by i2CAT, this space is available to the consortium as a streamlined solution for sharing and preserving project results while facilitating compliance with Horizon Europe open access mandates.

The platform provides single, trusted repository for data, software (optional, other options are under evaluation in GENOME), and public deliverables simplifying collaboration while as said above, the system ensures strict compliance with **Horizon Europe open science** requirements and **FAIR principles** integrating directly with the EU Open Research Repository and OpenAIRE to streamline reporting in the EC Participant Portal.

Figure 5: GENOME's community in Zenodo

Note: to ensure that uploads are automatically linked to the European Commission's reporting portal, when using the Zenodo community partners should include the GENOME grant agreement number in the 'Funding' field during submission.

6.3 Output reporting.

It is a contractual obligation for the members of the consortium to inform of any foreseen publication with at least 45 days in advance. Objections must be done within 30 days after the reception of the notice.

In addition, publications, conferences, book chapters, assistance to workshops, conferences, seminars and any other event linked with the dissemination have to be reported to through a dedicated [excel file](#)¹⁴ that reproduces the contents of the *Continuous Reporting Module* in the Participant Portal [Ref. 7]:

¹² Partners have to check the policy of their target journal to clear that a preprint or postprint will not pre-empt its publication

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/genome-101226860/>

¹⁴ Notice to the attention of the EU officers and external reviewers: this URL links direct to a file in the project Repository and thus with access limited to the project consortium members. The documentation is available under demand, contact pmo@i2cat.net

6.5 Project website and Social Networks

The official project web site¹⁵ and Social Networks are jointly managed by the Task 7.1 Leaders, the Project Coordinator (PC), and the Administrative Project Manager (APM). These parties are granted administrative credentials and are responsible for the regular curation of content. The website serves as the definitive, up-to-date repository for all public-facing project information.

To maintain this standard, partners will:

- Contribute material promptly: Provide the latest updates, findings, and media as they become available.
- Reference official channels in all individual public communications.
- Provide content administrators with relevant information regarding publications, press releases, and presentations (including dates, locations, media sources, and objectives).

To streamline this process, the Task 7.1 Leader will provide standardized, easy-to-use forms within the Project Repository to facilitate information submission.

Figure 7: GENOME project web and Social Networks QR code

7. DC’s Recruitment Guidelines

To attract top-tier global talent, the MSCA-DN recruitment process must be merit-based, transparent, and fair. As detailed in Table 1, a Recruitment Committee will be established during the first quarter to oversee the hiring process. The Committee will ensure full compliance with EU MSCA requirements regarding position descriptions and international advertising—and will provide collaborative assessment to assist recruiting institutions in the final selection of DCs.

The GENOME project consortium is committed to using the Job Applications platform set up by the Coordination the sole entry point for receiving all applications.

Figure 8: GENOME job application platform entry point

¹⁵ [REDACTED]

Figure 9: GENOME job application dashboard

The platform's dashboard is accessible to recruitment partners, allowing to easily download and review all candidate information.

The below sub-sections combine the essential requirements for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), focusing on fair recruitment and high-standard working conditions for Doctoral Candidates (DCs).

7.1 Best practices for recruitment

To ensure a fair and competitive selection process, GENOME recruitment partners adhere to the following to the following postulates:

- **Transparency and Outreach:** advertise positions globally (e.g., via [Euraxess¹⁶](https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/)) with clear details on gross salary and the Country Correction Coefficient (CCC) listed in the applicable Work Programme [Ref. 3].
- **Eligibility Check:** candidates must not have a PhD at the time of recruitment and must meet the MSCA DN mobility rule:

Candidates must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in the country of the recruiting organisation for more than 12 months in the 36 months immediately before their recruitment date.

- **Merit-Based Selection:** follow the *Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers* [Ref. 12] to ensure the process is open, well-documented, and free from conflicts of interest.
- **Strategic Planning:** account for lengthy administrative tasks, such as **visa processing** [Ref. 13], by starting early and maintaining a reserve list of candidates.

¹⁶ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/>

7.2 Contracting & working conditions

The employment framework is designed to protect the researcher’s rights and ensure institutional eligibility for funding. In compliance with the MSCA DN guidelines and regulations, the following measures are of application in GENOME:

- DCs must have a **full-time employment contract** (or equivalent) that includes **full social security and pension rights**.
- It is **mandatory to translate the contract**, so the researcher fully understands their rights and obligations.
- **Mandated MSCA allowances must be paid in full** (subject to local taxes). Precise financial records and supporting documents are required for audits.
- **Institutional Support:** HR departments must actively guide candidates through their benefits, salary structures, and administrative needs.
- **Enrolment in a doctoral program** is a mandatory requirement for all candidates.
- Candidates must be **physically hosted** at the beneficiary's premises to guarantee proper local supervision and integration into the research community.

8. Gender Neutral Guidelines¹⁷

This section provides guidelines to assist the integration of gender (and diversity) dimensions during the project implementation, in research activities.

These guidelines are based on the **EC gender equality strategy¹⁸** and aim at assisting the development of the work by rethinking standards, and questioning norms, behaviour, and attitudes, to best suit the needs of the target groups, thus strengthening the impact proposed by GENOME.

8.1 Terms of Reference for Gender-neutrality

GENOME adopts several terms of reference derived from the European Union Gender Equality Glossary and Thesaurus¹⁹, listed in the below Table 5:

Table 5: Gender-neutrality terms of reference

Term	Definition
Gender neutral language	Language that is not gender-specific, and which considers people in general without references to sex, gender, and gender bias.
Gender-sensitive language	Gender equality in written and spoken language, attained when men, women, and non-binary genders are equality made visible and referenced to with equal value, dignity, integrity, respect.

¹⁷ A significant portion of the content in this section was originally authored by **Dr. Rute Sofia (fortiss GmbH)** within the framework of CODECO, an Advanced Computing and Big Data project funded by the EU HE-GA n° 101092696. Dr. Sofia has kindly consented to the sharing and reuse of this material. The current version is the result of subsequent adaptations by **i2CAT** for use in further Project Management Handbooks. While the original framework belongs to Dr. Sofia, any errors or omissions in this adaptation are solely the responsibility of the current authors.

¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/just/items/682425/en>

¹⁹ <https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus>

Gender	Social attributes and opportunities associated with being female and male and to the relationships between women and men, girls, and boys, as well as to the relations between women and those between men.
Gender Bias	Prejudiced actions or thoughts based on the gender-based perception that women are not equal to men in rights and dignity.
Sex	Biological and physiological characteristics that define humans as female or male.
Gender stereotype	Generalised ideas, images, concepts about people within a society. A gender stereotype is a preconceived idea where women and men are assigned characteristics and roles determined and limited by their gender.

8.2 Gender Approach in the Project Implementation

In GENOME, there are four categories of activities that are expected to benefit from a gender-sensitive research and implementation approach: the **project management and coordination**; the **project communication and dissemination**; the **Training activities** and the **development of technologies** and their integration. Measures to assist gender-neutrality across the different activities, and verification measures to ensure an adequate quality level are provided by the European Institute for Gender Equality. Gender Sensitive Language [Ref. 14].

Table 6: Gender-neutrality proposed methodology and verification measures

Activity	Gender methodology	Implementation measures
Technologies (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define use-cases based on a design strategy that pays attention to sex, gender, and biases. • Understand and explore how the tools to be developed can help the GENOME stakeholders in understanding gender biases and eventually in modifying behaviour. • Design and implement the GENOME solutions in a way that it can be accessed by different groups and as many people as feasible, independently of background. • Consider impact assessment measures (for the activities developed) that can assess the gender dimension, interest, and impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt gender-neutral coding rules in the Deliverables (refer to section Gender-neutral Communication and Dissemination). • Synthetic Data: If real-world data is biased, consider using synthetic data generation to "balance" the scales before training begins. • Attribute Neutralization: When gender is not a necessary variable for the outcome, ensure it is "blinded" or removed from the model's features to prevent proxy discrimination.
Training (WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propose specific activities to involve women. • Ensure that participants samples is heterogeneous enough to best capture the needs and interests of each target group. • Develop plans for action to avoid gender bias, including required adaptations in the technology, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse Case Studies to ensure that all technical examples or datasets used in training sessions represent various genders and avoid stereotypical roles • Analyse and develop a methodology that takes into consideration the development of gender-neutral algorithmic and AI

Activity	Gender methodology	Implementation measures
	environment that is directed to underrepresented groups.	solutions, to prevent AI Discrimination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address gender bias as in specific events within T5.2: focused sessions on gender studies theories, methodologies, and research approaches.
Project Management (WP6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor and analyse the involvement of female researchers in the project, including within the DCs. • Ensure that men, women and non-binary persons of the different stakeholders can benefit equally from the GENOME results. • Ensure that project activities, staffing, and decision-making structures are inclusive of all genders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a gender analysis section on each Periodic Reporting. • Gender-Neutral Job Descriptions: Use unbiased language • Monitor deliverables and establish gender-neutral guidelines for deliverable and code writing.
Communication and Dissemination (WP7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the visibility and representation of women, when communicating and disseminating results. • Ensure balance and diversity on events organized by GENOME, in terms of Committees, evaluators, and participants. • Adopt mechanisms to advertise and promote events and activities, encouraging the participation of underrepresented groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a section on deliverables of WP7, analysing the gender involvement and gender bias dimension, as well as perceived usefulness of GENOME by different genders in the different deliverables • Neutral Imagery: Ensure website photos, brochures, and presentations represent a diverse range of scientists and avoid gender stereotypes.

8.3 Gender-neutral Communication and Dissemination

The EC provides guidelines for gender-neutral language [Ref. 14], based on principles of gender neutrality and non-discrimination. GENOME’s partners adopt such rules in the writing of any outcome, to ensure that, as far as possible, non-sexist and gender-inclusive language is adopted in the implementation of the project.

The guidelines proposed in this section are considered a starting point, which can be revised and modified during the project, based on the partners and stakeholders feedback, for instance. These guidelines are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7: Gender-neutral guidelines for the project implementation

Aspect	Gender-neutral GENOME approach
Generic use of masculine nouns that define a part to represent the whole,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Man → Humanity • Manpower → staff • Manmade → synthetic, artificial

<p>Masculine pronouns, e.g., his</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use plural forms. • Omit the pronoun (the work is dependent on his stay – the work is dependent on the length of the stay) • Use the passive voice. • If none works, adopt “he or she”.
<p>Ensure all genders are represented</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure all genders (including non-binary) are represented in all surveys, forms, feedback, or consent from stakeholders. • Ensure different genders take roles that are traditionally envisioned to a specific gender, e.g., consider an equal balance from different genders in panels. • Develop dissemination material (videos, photos, images) taking into consideration diversity (of gender and others). • Explain, in the organization of events, how the different gender representation will be captured.
<p>Avoid gender stereotypes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid language including gendered pronouns, nouns. • Avoid gendered stereotypes as descriptive terms. • Avoid gendering inanimate objects. • Avoid using different adjectives for women and men. • Avoid social stereotypes (e.g., in a use-case, considering a specific female traditional roles vs a male traditional role).
<p>Avoid omission</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid the use of man as a neutral term. • Do not use gender-biased nouns to refer to groups of people. • Consider the choice of voice-overs, photos/images, and the gender of individuals given in examples when creating communication and dissemination material. • Ensure a balanced gender (and diversity) representation in speaking, representation, and participation roles.
<p>Avoid subordination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid language that reinforce a traditional role of a gender, e.g., men’s traditional dominance over women. • Always use the same naming conventions for men and women • Avoid objectification

8.4 Addressing Gender Aspect in Research

This final section depicts a checklist for the development of research activities within the GENOME project that takes into consideration gender-neutrality, derived from the Toolkit Gender in EU-funded research published by the EC, Directorate-General for and Innovation [Ref. 15] and the video “Understanding gender dimension for MSCA projects” published by the EU in the Science & Innovation youtube channel [Ref. 16].

Research idea phase:

- If the research involves humans as research objects, has the gender dimension been analysed?

Methodology:

- Does the methodology ensure that gender aspects will be considered in data collected, and such aspects will be adequately documented?
- Does the respective deliverable/paper/etc explicitly and comprehensively explain how gender issues will be handled?
- Does the research consider different outcome and different impact in terms of gender?

Research development:

- Does this phase consider surveys, focus groups, etc., designed to unravel potentially relevant sex and/or gender differences in the data?
- Are the groups involved in the research adequately gender-balanced?
- Is the data collected and analysed adequately set to integrate balance in terms of gender?

Dissemination and communication:

- Does the research analysis present statistics, output, focusing on relevant gender differences that came up during the research development?
- Do the stakeholders consider specific entities that focus on gender aspects?
- Does this phase contemplate the organization of specific events/sub-programmes addressing underrepresented groups?

9. Definitions

Beneficiaries	The organisations signatories of the EC-GA receiving EU funding in the form of a Unit Costs grant.
Consortium Agreement	Means the agreement concluded amongst GENOME <i>partners</i> for the implementation of the action. Such an agreement shall not affect the beneficiaries' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the contract.
Consortium	The GENOME Consortium, conformed by the organisations listed in Section 1 of the present document. For decision taking on <i>consortium</i> level serves the Supervisory Board of the Consortium.
Continuous Reporting Module	At the beginning of each project, the continuous reporting module is activated through the Participant Portal for the beneficiaries to submit deliverables, to report on progress in achieving milestones, to answer to the questionnaire on different issues as soon as their own data are available.
Deliverable	A report that is sent to the Commission or Agency providing information to ensure effective monitoring of the project. There are different types of deliverables (e.g. a report on specific activities or results, data management plans, ethics or security requirements).
Dissemination	The public disclosure of the results by appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.

Grant Agreement	The grant MSCA-DN contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. The contract itself is signed by the coordinator and the European Commission; the rest of beneficiaries' access to the grant by signing the accession form
(EU) Participant Portal (Grants Management System)	Former name for the Funding and Tender Opportunities portal: EU website where EU bodies and beneficiaries manage EU funding. Unique entry point for all EU funds/funding programmes that are part of eGrants and eProcurement
Partner	Consortium member having signed the Accession to the Grant Agreement and/or participating as Associated Partner and signing the Consortium Agreement
Project Workplan	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the <i>consortium</i> and their time schedule, according to EU-GA.
(Research) output	Results generated by the action to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, data or other engineered outcomes and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols and electronic notebooks.
Work package	Major sub-divisions of the project with a verifiable end-point which should follow the logical phases of the implementation of the project

10. References²⁰

- Ref. 1 [Horizon Europe \(HORIZON\) HE Programme Guide](#) version 5.1, 15 September 2025
- Ref. 2 [Horizon Europe \(HORIZON\) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions – Financial Guide](#), version 1.0, December 2023
- Ref. 3 [Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2025 for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions](#), European Commission Decision C(2025) 2779 of 14 May 2025
- Ref. 4 [Horizon Europe \(HORIZON\) Model Grant Agreement, Unit MGA – Multi & Mono](#) version 1.3, December 2025
- Ref. 5 [REDACTED]
- Ref. 6 [REDACTED]
- Ref. 7 [REDACTED]
- Ref. 8 [REDACTED]
- Ref. 9 Zenodo community of the project <https://zenodo.org/communities/genome-101226860/>

²⁰ Notice to the attention of the EU officers and external reviewers: most of the below URL links direct to the project Repository and thus with access limited to the project consortium members. The documentation is available under demand, contact pmo@i2cat.net

- Ref. 10 [REDACTED]
- Ref. 11 [REDACTED]
- Ref. 12 In 2005, the European Commission adopted a European [Charter for Researchers](#) and a [Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers](#). These documents, which apply to researchers, employers, and funders in both the public and private sectors, are essential components of the EU's policy to support and enhance researchers' careers.
- Ref. 13 [Directive \(EU\) 2016/801](#), sets harmonized entry and residence conditions for non-EU nationals for studies and research. It remains in force in 2026, with key provisions continuing to facilitate mobility across Member States (except Denmark and Ireland).
- Ref. 14 European Institute for Gender Equality. Gender Sensitive Language. Available at: <https://eige.europa.eu/publications/gender-sensitive-communication/first-steps-towards-more-inclusive-language>
- Ref. 15 European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. European Toolkit Gender in EU Research. October 2011. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c17a4eba-49ab-40f1-bb7b-bb6faaf8dec8>
- Ref. 16 [Understanding gender dimension for MSCA projects](#) in the Youtube EU Science & Innovation

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